

THE METHODOLOGY OF LEARNING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN SCHOOLS AND THE ADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Kushiyeva Fatima Ergashevna

Uzbek language teacher, school 83,
Mirabad district, Tashkent

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Abstract: This article deals with the use of information technologies in learning the Uzbek language in schools is presented not only at various stages of training schoolchildren, but also the possibility of using computers and electronic resources in regular Uzbek language classes.

Keywords: language, learning the Uzbek language, modern computers, electronic resources, the internet, new materials, reinforcement, repetition, knowledge management, teaching skills and competencies.

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After the independence of our country, the demand for learning languages increased sharply, wide opportunities for language learning are being created in our country. Today, schools have modern computers, electronic resources and the internet. The introduction of computer technologies into the traditional lesson scheme allows the teacher to work in the computer part of the educational process, the educational process becomes more interesting, colorful, intense.

Attracting students to the computer makes any lesson attractive and truly modern. It creates an opportunity to perform any task, use the computer, and increase the intensity of the lesson. Use of variable materials and operational plans help individualize learning. It can be used at all stages of computer-assisted teaching in the Uzbek language class: new materials, reinforcement, repetition, knowledge management, teaching of skills and competencies.

Today we will discuss in detail about distance learning of the Uzbek language, its features that differ from regular classes, and the benefits of IT in remote learning of the Uzbek language.

Speaking about specific features, it is necessary to emphasize the advantages of distance education available to all participants of the educational process (teacher and student): access to various sources of information; the ability to receive information of different sizes and contents; the ability to quickly communicate and exchange data of any size and type over any distance; ability to learn and complete assignments on an individual basis; the possibility of switching from oral teaching methods to methods of partial research, science and creative activity of students;

the ability to significantly increase students' interest in learning Uzbek language, which affects memory, emotions, motivational field, ability to learn computer skills.

The goal of distance education in the Uzbek language class is not to teach ready-made facts and actions, but to teach the principles of orientation in the educational material, first of all, with the help of sources. The ability to work with information arrays, find the necessary information, analyze it competently and use it for various purposes of knowledge - all this is becoming one of the main types of cognitive activity of students in modern and future schools.

The meaning of education is to create conditions for each student's learning, self-study, education, self-education and development - creative self-development. Indispensable conditions for self-development are the development of independence and creativity, responsibility, initiative and personal educational activity. The student should evaluate the importance and difficulty of tasks, the time and effort spent, predict the possible consequences and results of his educational activities. In the process of distance education, the student himself becomes the creator of his education, he plans, organizes and analyzes his actions. All this is consistent with the main goal of learning - teaching to learn.

An online distance lesson - is a tool for distance learning system and course creation over the internet. The system has the necessary capabilities for teaching and teachers to create courses, control and conduct courses. It is intended for distance education in educational institutions and schools, as well as distance training and retraining of specialists in private enterprises. It consists of the following systems: registration, creation and editing of distance learning courses, teaching, communication, news. With the help of the system, the teacher can create, edit, constantly update and conduct courses, accept and remove students from the course.

With the help of the system, the student can always study individually, regardless of time and place of residence. Usually, the student acquires knowledge by reading, completing assignments, observing, sharing experience, making mistakes and correcting them, thinking and teaching others. Using the network in teaching makes it transformative. With the help of the system, it is possible to work together and participate in discussions regardless of distance. The system has several advantages. In this case, the student has the opportunity to communicate individually with the teacher, with other students, and with the administration. Online reading includes postings, offline and online discussions. This gives the teacher and students an opportunity to discuss common questions and questions of each student. The student works both individually and collaboratively. Each student will have a general and personal goal. It is these possibilities that create a virtual learning group.

Decree No. PF – 3080 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2002 “On further development of computerization and introduction of information communication technologies” and Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers on June 6, 2002 “On further development of computerization and introduction of information communication technologies” Resolution No. 200 “on measures” made it possible to further develop work in this regard on the portal. In order to ensure the implementation of this decree and decision, this page was created and put into use.

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